

Checklist: Versioning

- A „master file“ has been created and measures taken to maintain its authenticity, i.e. access rights and responsibilities are defined - who is entitled to make what kind of changes?
- Differences between common versions of researchers and working versions of individuals have been clarified.
- It is decided how many versions of a file should be kept, which versions should be kept (e.g. major versions instead of minor versions (version 2.0 but not 2.01)), how long and how versions should be organized.
- A clear and systematic naming of file versions and editions has been introduced.
- Relationships between elements, e.g. between code and the data file needed for execution, between data file and associated documentation or metadata, or between multiple files have been captured as needed.
- Changes in every version are documented.
- Original versions of files are kept, or the documentation of it is kept so that original files can be reconstructed.
- Files are regularly synchronized at different locations.
- The conditions for the use of the data have been established and communicated to the team members and other users.

Sources:

- CESSDA Training Working Group. CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC, 2017-2018, <https://www.cessda.eu/DMGuide>. Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License
- Dolzycka, Dominika, Biernacka, Katarzyna, Helbig, Kerstin, & Buchholz, Petra. (2019). Train-the-Trainer Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 2.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2581292> Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
- Krejčí, Jindřich. Introduction to the Management of Social Survey Data. Praha: Sociologický ústav AV ČR, v.v.i.64 s. 2014. ISBN 978-80-7330-252-8
- Corti, Louise, Veerle Van den Eynden, Libby Bishop und Matthew Woollard. Managing and Sharing Research Data: A Guide to Good Practice. Los Angeles, CA: SAGE, 2014.